

**RISK FACTORS AND PREVALENCE OF OVERWEIGHT AMONG
HEALTH WORKERS IN MULAGO NATIONAL REFERRAL
HOSPITAL KAMPALA, UGANDA.**

BIRABWA JALIA

**MASTER OF PUBLIC HEALTH
(Nutrition)**

OCTOBER, 2021

**RISK FACTORS AND PREVALENCE OF OVERWEIGHT AMONG
HEALTH WORKERS IN MULAGO NATIONAL REFERRAL
HOSPITAL KAMPALA, UGANDA.**

**BIRABWA JALIA
18/MPH/BU/G/1002**

**A Thesis Submitted to School of Graduate Studies Bugema University in Partial
Fulfilment of Requirements for the Award of Master
Degree in Public Health (Nutrition)**

OCTOBER, 2021

ACCEPTANCE SHEET

This Thesis is entitled, “**RISK FACTORS AND PREVALENCE OF OVERWEIGHT AMONG HEALTH WORKERS IN MULAGO NATIONAL REFERRAL HOSPITAL KAMPALA, UGANDA**” prepared and submitted by **BIRABWA JALIA**, in partial fulfillment of the requirement for the degree of **MASTER OF PUBLIC HEALTH** is here by accepted.

Prof. David Ndungutse
Chairperson, Advisory Committee

Date Signed

Christopher Ddamulira, MPH, Dr.PH (PhD)
Member, Advisory Committee

Date Signed

Assoc. Prof. Nazarius M. Tumwesigye **Micheal Wolwa, MD, MPH**
Chairperson, External Examination Committee Member, Internal Examination Committee

Date Signed

Date Signed

Accepted as a partial fulfilment of the requirements for the degree of **MASTER OF PUBLIC HEALTH**, Bugema University

Fredrick Ndoboli, MBCHB, MPH
Chairperson, Department of Public Health

Date Signed

Rosette Kabuye, Ph.D.
Dean, School of Graduate Studies

Date Signed

DECLARATION

I, **BIRABWA JALIA** declare that this thesis represents my own work, which has not been submitted for a Master’s degree in Bugema University or any other institution of higher learning for an academic award.

Signature

BIRABWA JALIA

Researcher

.....

Date Signed

DEDICATION

This thesis is dedicated to my lovely children, relatives and friends for their moral and spiritual support through my study session. God bless them and protect them all the time.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

I would like to express my deep gratitude to my research supervisors; Prof. David Ndungutse and Dr. Ddamulira Christopher for their patient guidance, enthusiastic encouragement and useful critiques toward the accomplishment of this work.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS/ACRONYMS

AOR:	Adjusted Odds Ratio
BMI:	Body Mass Index
CDC:	Centre for Disease Control
COR:	Crude Odds Ratio
GWG:	Gestational Weight Gain
H/W:	Health Workers
IRB:	Institutional Review Board
WHO:	World Health Organization

ABSTRACT

BIRABWA JALIA, School of Graduate Studies, Bugema University, November 2020. Thesis title; **RISK FACTORS AND PREVALENCE OF OVERWEIGHT AMONG HEALTH WORKERS IN MULAGONATIONAL REFERRAL HOSPITAL KAMPALA, UGANDA**

Supervisor: Prof David Ndungutse

The study was carried out in Mulago National Referral Hospital, Kampala, Uganda. It was specifically set to investigate the prevalence and Risk factors for overweight among the health workers in Mulago National Referral Hospital, and to establish the association between the risk factors and overweight among the health workers in Mulago National Referral Hospital. The study employed both quantitative and qualitative research approaches using Cross sectional descriptive and correlational research designs. The study collected data from 306 participants that were selected by stratified simple random sampling. The data was collected by structured questionnaire that was self-administered by the participants. The data was analysed at descriptive, bivariate and multivariate levels in STATA Version 14.0

Findings indicated **smoking** AOR= 2.527;95% CI:[0.868-7.358-9.85], $P = 0.089$ and **supervisory position** AOR= 0.732[0.367-1.457], $P=0.374$ were insignificant factors, while **Age** of 30-39year AOR=2.110;95%,CI; [1.025-4.346], $p= 0.043$; 40-49years AOR=2.324,95%, CI:[1.107-4.876]; $P=0.026$; ≥ 49 years AOR=3.094,95%, CI:[1.355-11.249]; $P=0.012$,**Bodyinctiveness**,AOR=1.923,95%,CI:[1.127-3.279] $P=0.016$ and **wrong perception** AOR=0.533,95%,CI:[0.0304-0.934], $P=0.028$ were the significant factors associated with overweight among the health workers in Mulago National Referral Hospital Kampala Uganda.

In conclusion, the health workers of Mulago National Referral Hospital had a high prevalence of overweight of 72.5% which poses a risk for non-communicable diseases. The researcher suggests that the available recommended physical activity strategy should be strengthened among the health workers e.g. by providing structures and time for carrying out body exercises at all health facilities and health workers should be provided with continuous sensitisation about the health-related issues regarding overweight and the importance of routine physical exercises prior age of 30years and on set of overweight.

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

Overweight has become a public health challenge worldwide. Overweight is when there is excessive fat accumulation in the body. It is determined by Body mass index (BMI) which is a person's weight in kilograms divided by the square of the person's height in meters (kg/m²). World Health organization (WHO) categorizes BMI as follows; 18.5-24.9 kg/m² Normal, 25.0 -30 kg/m² overweight and >30 kg/m² obese. WHO (2016), reported a prevalence of 1.9 billion overweight among of adults and It presents a risk of non-communicable diseases such as cardiovascular diseases, diabetes mellitus and cancers etc. that accounts for 70% early deaths worldwide (Blüher, M. (2019). Therefore, overweight might continue to be a public health challenge if no interventions are made.

Health workers not only includes nurses but other health professionals such as Doctors, Midwives, Lab technicians, who as a whole Pharmacists are expected to be on the frontline for Health promotion of health life styles in both prevention of communicable and non-communicable diseases. They go through a training to equip them with knowledge and skills. However, research reported that health workers are also affected by such lifestyle conditions related to overweight. Gupta & Gaur (2016), reported 54.5% prevalence of overweight among nurses internationally. Similarly, Kyle *et al.*, (2016) found higher incidence of overweight among the Scottish nurses with 69.1% and Wills *et al.*, (2017), reported 25.12% of overweight among the Nurses in England. Thus, medical professionals are as well affected by

lifestyle condition of overweight irrespective of their key position in the prevention measures.

Overweight was found to exist among the African health professionals. Dankyau *et al.*, (2016), reported prevalence 64% of overweight among health workers in the Eastern Cape Province of South Africa. In the same way Daniel *et al.*, (2019), reported 18% prevalence of overweight among the nurses while Kingue *et al.*, (2015), found 30.3% prevalence of overweight among the medical workers compared to 23.5% of the general population in Cameroon (Kingue *et al.*, 2015). The Medical personnel's in Africa were identified with overweight.

In East Africa, some studies reported overweight among the health workers. According to Ondicho *et al.*, (2016), found 58.8% prevalence rate among the health workers in Kisumu East Sub-County, Kenya. While Mutanda *et al.*, (2017) reported a prevalence of 45.5% of overweight among the nurses in Mulago National Referral Hospital. This study focused on nurses only that are a portion of the health work force that consists of various health professional like doctors, dentists, midwives etc. Therefore, the study revealed an ice burg of overweight among the health worker force. However, Ismail (2019) reported that in Arua Referral Hospital the majority of the workers 72% had a normal BMI and only 21% were overweight. Some medical workers in east Africa were identified with increase BMI.

Some of the previous studies done among the health professionals revealed relationships between the risk factors and overweight. The identified risk factors included; individual, social demographics and occupational factors. Some of the reported individual factors for overweight among the health workers included; skipping meals, junk food consumption, lack of enough body exercise, alcohol use, smoking, perception and knowledge gap (Florindo *et al.*, 2015; Maria *et al.*, 2017;

Monakali *et al.*, 2019). The identified Social demographic factors included; age, sex, low economic status, house hold capacity and being married (Lim *et al.* and Taib, (2019); Ondicho *et al.*, 2016). Additionally, shift work schedule, time in service and supervisory position were the occupational risk factors (Monakali *et al.*, 2019 and Samhat *et al.*, 2020). Numerous researches identified different risk factors linked with overweight among the medical staff.

The health workers in Mulago National Referral Hospital are likely to be affected by increased BMI Mutanda *et al.*, (2017) assessed the prevalence and factors associated with musculoskeletal disorders among nurses in Mulago National Referral hospital with a sample size of 226 and identified that 45.5% of the Nurses were overweight with muscular disorder. The study done in Arua Regional Referral Hospital objectively to identify the prevalence and risk factors for overweight among the employees, reported that the majority of the health workers 72% had normal BMI, and only 21% were overweight (Ismail, 2019). This study focused on the general health workers in Arua Referral Hospital but concluded no problem of overweight among the workers. However, the study done in Mulago National Referral Hospital that focused majorly on nurses who are a portion of the health worker force, reported overweight prevalence of 45.5%. Therefore, this implied that overweight might be a problem among the general health workers in Mulago National Referral Hospital.

Statement of the Problem

Health professionals undergo training to equip them with knowledge and skills in advocacy for health promotion. However, research found 45.5% prevalence of overweight among the health workers in Mulago National referral Hospital Mutand *et al.*, (2017). This prevalence was found to be greater than 25.12% prevalence of over-

weight that was reported among the health workers in England (Wills *et al.*, 2017) and also it was almost twice to the prevalence of 21% that was reported among the general health workers in Arua Regional Referral Hospital Adam, I. (2019). Overweight generally is related to a number of health complications. Overweight is the leading cause of non-communicable diseases such as; hypertension, diabetes mellitus, some types of cancers and it accounted for 38 million annual deaths (WHO, 2002). Moreover, it reduced the medical workers' productivity through increased absenteeism that eventually leads to high indirect cost (Goettler *et al.*, 2017). For example, overweight health workers were estimated to cost employers \$644 compared to \$201 of the staff who had normal BMI (Goetzel *et al.*, 2010). Overweight health workers faced challenges in delivering health promotion messages and implementation of strategic interventions for overweight prevention (Mc Dowell *et al.*, Gupta and Gaur, 2016). Control [CDC], (2011), provided a number of guidelines on health diet and exercises etc. Unfortunately, remarkable rise of overweight was reported among the health workers in Mulago National Referral hospital. There was limited literature to exactly understand what was happening among the health workers in relation to overweight in Mulago National Referral Hospital. Therefore, this study aimed to investigate the prevalence and risk factors for overweight among health workers in Mulago national referral hospital Kampala, Uganda. Otherwise, overweight would continue escalating among the health workers.

Research Questions

This study attempted to answer the following questions:

- 1) What were the characteristics of individual and occupational factors among the health workers in Mulago National Referral Hospital?

- 2) What was the proportion of overweight among the health workers in Mulago National Hospital?
- 3) What Individual and occupational factors were associated with and overweight among the health workers in Mulago Referral Hospital?

General Objective

The general objective of this study was to investigate the risk factors for overweight among the health workers in Mulago National Referral Hospital, to guide policy development and strategic interventions.

Specific Objectives

- 1) To describe the characteristics of individual and occupational factors among the Health workers in Mulago National Referral Hospital.
- 2) To determine the prevalence of overweight among the health workers in Mulago National Referral Hospital Kampala, Uganda.
- 3) To establish whether individual and occupational factors were associated with overweight among the Health workers in Mulago National Referral Hospital.

Hypothesis of the Study

The null hypothesis states that, there is no significant association between Individual and Occupational factors with overweight among health workers in Mulago National Referral Hospital, Kampala, Uganda.

Scope of the Study

The study was carried out in Mulago National Referral Hospital from the 2 geographical locations of Kawempe and Mulago hill health facilities. It examined the Risk factors and prevalence of overweight among health workers of Mulago

National Referral Hospital, Kampala, Uganda. The factors examined were Individual and occupational factors. The study area selection was based on the study done by Mutanda *et al.*, (2017) who reported a prevalence of overweight of 45.5% among the health workers in the Mulago National Hospital, Kampala Uganda. This study was a land mark to unfold an iceberg of overweight among a proportion of health workers. Data collection got started from 22 Nov-31 Dec 2020 (4weeks), data cleaning and analysis took 4weeks and report writing (4weeks). The project took a total of 12 weeks. The current study site was operated in two sites of Mulago National Referral Hospital, Kampala, Uganda.

Limitations of the Study

The current research encountered some constraints during it operations. This research was a cross-sectional research design that provided information about the prevalence of outcome variable but it was difficult to derive causal relationships between the independent and dependant variables. Also, analysis by carder was not done because carder variables were not included in the conceptual framework. Moreover, the study adopted a quantitative research approach solely that could not get a deep understanding of the respondent's opinions about the problem.

Non-response bias was realized when some respondents included in the sample did not reply to some fields in the questionnaire. This might have been generally due to unintentional skip of the questions. Various ways were considered to reduce non-response bias like the internal and external validity, seeking consent prior data collection, ensuring confidentiality and quality control level one etc. Nonetheless, it happened during the process whereby non-responses were identified later after the research assistant left the field yet this was a one point in time study.

Recall bias (a systematic error that occurs when participants do not remember previous events or experiences accurately or omit details) might have been incurred in this study. The current study asked participants about past exposures especially their physical exercise and eating habits. Much as this was minimised by limiting their exposure in the last one-week, human memory might have been burdened with a lot of thoughts and activities that might have made them to forget. The stratified simple random sampling used and improved the representativeness of particular strata within the population. However, it was a puzzle to gain access to the records due to protection by Human resource to create a final list from which the sample was selected and to reach the respondents due to the varied geographical locations and work shift schedules of the population.

Significance of the Study

The findings of this study will be of great value to various stakeholders:

Ministry of Health: The information contributed to the already existing knowledge in the academic world and could be used for program planning and policy development aimed at preventing over weight among health workers.

Hospital: The administration got to know the nutritional status of its staff that may prompt some local interventions development or improvement

Health Workers: They got aware of their BMI status which might make them start taking preventive or management measures.

Researcher: The investigator gained experience in research process and in the achievement of the ward of a master's degree.

Theoretical Framework

The study employed a Social Cognitive Theory (SCT) as a tool that scientists use to try and predict health behaviours. It posits that learning occurs in a social context with a dynamic and reciprocal interaction of the person, environment, and behaviour. It suggests that an individual behaviour can be influenced by personal, social and environmental factors (Bandura, 1968). The following are the constructs of the SCT:

Reciprocal Determinism This refers to the dynamic and reciprocal interaction of person (individual with a set of learned experiences), environment (external social context), and behaviour (responses to stimuli to achieve goals). People will not change their health behaviour or use a recommended intervention unless they believe that they are at risk of acquiring a disease. *Example:* Those who do not think that they are at risk of acquiring any of the non-communicable diseases related to overweight are unlikely to take health measures maintaining a healthy weight. Simfukwe *et al.* (2017) showed that the respondents recognised the awareness of their unhealthy food choices that could lead to overweight and its related health consequences.

Behavioural Capability - This refers to a person's actual ability to display certain behaviour through essential knowledge and skills. In order to successfully display such behaviour, a person must know what to do and how to do it. People learn from the consequences of their behaviour, which also affects the environment in which they live. People are less likely to consider health food choices and physical body activity when they have no knowledge about the health foods and skills for body exercises. Moreover, they might decide to take on health lifestyle to maintain healthy weight only if they are aware of the health consequences of Overweight. Simfukwe *et al.*,

(2017), revealed that the health workers who were aware of the risk factors of overweight were able to take health lifestyle to maintain healthy weight.

Observational Learning - This asserts that people can witness and observe behaviour displayed by others, and then reproduce those actions. This is often exhibited through "modelling" of behaviours. If individuals see successful demonstration of a given behaviour, they can also display the behaviour successfully. Example, Simfukwe *et al.*, (2017), reported that some health workers were influenced by the observed behaviour in the community, whereby people with good economic status were recognised with respect as they consumed takeaway food from fast food outlets.

Reinforcements - This refers to the internal or external responses to a person's behaviour that affect the likelihood of continuing or discontinuing the behaviour. Reinforcements can be self-initiated or in the environment, and reinforcements can be positive or negative. Individuals may fail to sustain their health behaviours due to physical or social difficulties like effort, time and money etc. Research among health workers revealed that many demonstrated that the knowledgeable health professionals could consume unhealthy food because it was more accessibility than the naturally nutritious foods (Simfukwe *et al.*, 2017).

Expectations - This refers to the anticipated consequences of a person's behaviour. Outcome expectations can be health-related or not health-related. People anticipate the consequences of their actions before engaging in the behaviour, and these anticipated consequences can influence successful completion of the behaviour. Simfukwe *et al.*, (2017), reported that health workers who were conscious about their body appearance at work and in public places got motivation to change their lifestyle in response of maintaining a normal weight, and also posters on the notice boards

concerning complications of overweight with related diseases prompted the health workers to care about their health.

Furthermore, health workers that who had colleagues or family members diagnosed with NCDs were motivated to seek medical advice and to modify their lifestyles, to attend disease screening at clinics like the diabetic clinics, and change their unhealthy eating habits or to include daily exercise in their lives (Simfukwe *et al.*,2017).

Self-efficacy: This refers to the level of a person's confidence in his or her ability to successfully display certain behaviour. Self-efficacy is influenced by a person's specific capabilities and other individual factors, as well as by environmental factors (barriers and facilitators). Simfukwe *et al.*, (2017), reported that health workers set goals to attain in their exercising and eating programmes, and improved more when they noted improvements in their weight control programmes. Also, they felt a need for social support to continue exercising or to control their diets. Hence this model was suitable for this study because it addressed the study variables as indicated in the conceptual framework in which the independent variables were individual and occupational factors affecting dependent variable that was overweight.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

Operational Definition of Terms

Individual Factors:

Age In this study the age of the respondent referred to how old the respondent was at the time of the study. Age was measured in complete years.

Marital Status: In this study marital status meant any of the following types of marriages; customary, religious, civil and cohabiting. Single meant any of the following forms; never married, divorced, separated and widow and widower. Marital status was measured on a binary nominal scale where 1=Single 2= Married.

Gender: This meant either of the two sexes male or female and was measured as a binary nominal scale where 1=Male 2= Female.

Economic Status: This meant the total earnings of an individual on a monthly basis. It was measured as 1=100000-300000, 2=400000-600000, 3=700000-900000, 4=1000000 and above.

Household Capacity: This meant the total number of children and adults that share the same meals and house with the respondent. It was measured on binary scale where 1=below 5people, 2=5and above people.

Eating Habit: This meant the eating behaviours related to fast food consumption (sugary, oily), skipping meals and meal substitution. This was measured on a nominal scale. Where 1=yes for poor eating habit, 2=No for good eating habit.

Physical Exercise: This referred to whether respondents were involved in any moderate physical activity that causes small increase in breathing and heart rate. It was measured on binary nominal scale. 1= Yes to body active, 2= to body inactive.

Alcohol Consumption: This referred to drinking or use of alcoholic drinks. It was measured using the nominal scale where; 1=Yes alcohol consumption2=No alcohol consumption.

Smoking: This referred to use of tobacco products including manufactured cigarettes, hand rolled cigarettes or pipes full of tobacco. It was measured on a binary nominal scale where 1 =Yes (smokers), 2=No (Non-smoker).

Knowledge: This involved assessment of the understanding of the recommended physical exercise and BMI. This was measured by index score based on seven questions. The seven questions, those who will pass 6 and above questions were knowledgeable while below 6questions were not knowledgeable.

Perception: This meant people's beliefs or opinions regarding overweight and their eating habits. The opinions about BMI were measured on index scale of three questions with responses of Yes/No. Those who passed the 3 questions were

considered with wrong perception while below 3 were considered with correct perception.

Occupational Factors:

Duration in Service: This meant the number of years spent in the in the health service. This was measured on a nominal scale where by < *year* = 1, 1-5years =2, 6-10years =3, >10years =4

Work Shift: This meant the different kinds of work schedule that the staff usually followed as they performed their duties such as day, evening and night shifts. This was measured on a nominal scale, where 1=yes for Day, 2=Evening, 3=night 4=other

Supervisory Work: This meant staff in managerial level that occupied most of their time at work. This was measured on a binary 1 scale where 1=yes for supervisor, 2=No for supervisor

Overweight: This meant those with BMI of ≥ 25 .

Body Mass Index (BMI): This was used as a screening measure of overweight. It was calculated by dividing individual's weight in kilograms by height in metres squared (Weight in Kg/Height in M^2) and was measured using an interval scale: 1 =Underweight BMI <18.5), 2= Normal weight BMI (18.5-24.9 Kg/ M^2), 3=Over weight BMI (25-29.5 Kg/ M^2) and 4=obese BMI ≥ 30 Kg/ M^2)

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

This chapter contains literature on the risk factors and prevalence of overweight among health workers. The sources of Literature were published journals and articles. The purpose of literature review in this section was to review other researchers and scholars with aim of identifying the gaps. The prevalence of overweight and risk factors was the collected works confined in this section. Hence this chapter addresses the works of the previous scholars regarding the current study.

It is fundamental for health workers not only to serve the community's health needs but also to act as role models for a healthy lifestyle. Health workers are trained in various health matters to equip them with knowledge and skills to advocate for health life styles through health promotion to care receivers and public. Unfortunately, remarkable rise of overweight was found among health workers. There was limited literature to exactly understand what was happening among the health workers in relation to their increased BMI. Therefore, medical personnel should be the extemporary in the promoting health lifestyle.

Prevalence of Overweight

The increased BMI among the health workers was reported in various studies. Kyle *et al.*, (2017), found a higher Prevalence of overweight of 69.1% among the health workers in Scotland. Similarly, Ondicho *et al.*, (2016) reported 58.8%prevalence of overweight among the Kenyan healthcare workers in Kisumu East Sub County, and also Iwuala *et al.*, (2015), found 44.7% prevalence of overweight among health service providers (HSP) of a tertiary healthcare facility in

Lagos. The mentioned studies were crucial to understanding how the health workforce was affected by the overweight. Although health professionals are at the frontline in health promotion in the prevention of both communicable and non-communicable diseases, are as well affected by the on rise of the overweight.

Individual Factors

Age

The age of 40years above was reported by different studies to be a significant factor for overweight among the medical workers. Lim *et al.*, (2019) reported that age of 40 years and beyond was a predictor for overweight among the health staff in Malaysia. Similarly, Amougou *et al.*, (2019) and Ondicho *et al.*, (2016) reported that age of 40years beyond as a predictor for overweight for the health workers in Yaoundé Hospital and East Cape South Africa respectively. Hence the majority of the previous researchers revealed the age of 40 years above as a predictor factor for overweight.

The increased BMI as an individual advance in age was associated with some factors. The body muscle loss naturally begins to decline about 30 years and increases at age of 40years (Apovian, the Director of the Nutrition and Weight Management Centre at the Boston Medical Centre). The more muscle mass individuals possess, the more calories the body will burn. Therefore, a body requires fewer calories when there is muscle degeneration or else it leads to body fat accumulation. Additionally, older age comes with a general reduction in body activity. Gary, Hunt, VanderJagt, & Vellas (1992) found that as a people get older, they tend to reduce their body activities, yet their food consumption never reduces. This causes energy imbalance

between the carol intake and energy expenditure. Muscle loss is associated with a reduction in energy expenditure hence leading to weight gain.

Gender

Research done formerly by some scholars found a relationship between gender and overweight. Iwuala *et al.*, (2015) showed that female gender was significantly associated with overweight among the health workers in Nigeria. Similarly, Lim *et al.*, and Amougou *et al.* (2019); reported that female health workers were predictors for overweight. However, to the less extent Khan *et al.*, (2016) and Maria *et al.*, (2017) found Male gender to be a predictor factor for overweight among the medical students of Lahore in Pakistan and Mexico respectively.

The previously mentioned researches might have faced some shortcomings irrespective of the significant findings. Lim *et al.*, (2019) used a representative sample of the health workers from both urban and rural health facility setting. However, BMI calculation was based on the self-report of height and weight that might have compromised with the results. The current study weight and height were measured by the research assistants to get the actual estimate for BMI. While Khan *et al.*, (2016) and Maria *et al.*, (2017) studies were done among the young health professionals' students with average age of 21 years. The youth period is associated with the rapid growth of vital body organs that make them consume a lot of food to meet the body demand and if this is not balanced by body activity can easily lead over weight (Tanner, (1981). The current study was done among the adult working health workers with the average age of 38.7 years. Therefore, the method of anthropometric measure and age group for the study population, were some of the shortfalls in some previous studies.

There are some factors that might explain the female gender as a predictor for overweight in the above-mentioned studies. The above studies were done among the qualified health workers already in field with average of 35years and Female gender might lack time for leisure that impacts on their high weight compared to male gender. According to Pinto *et al.*, (2018) reported that Lack of personal and leisure time among females was highly linked to increased overweight compared to males. Furthermore, women are subjected to gestational weight gain (GWG) that is likely to persist and affect their BMI in their midlife time compared to men. Hutchins *et al.*, (2020), found that the prevalence of overweight at midlife was higher among women who had one or more excessive GWG pregnancies. Hence, the lack of leisure time, average age of 35years and gestational weight gain might have been some of the explanations for the significant association for overweight among the female gender in mentioned studies.

Similarly, there might have been factors for the male gender predictor for overweight in the mentioned studies. They found female to have low BMI compared to males might be explained by their physical outlook sensitivity, the young ladies might tend to be mindful about their body appearance than males. Gaylis *et al.* (2020) found that females endeavoured to take health diet majorly to keep attractive figure while male never minded about losing weight. The duty for the young ladies to keep being attractive physically might explain why in some studies done among the youth medical workers found the male with higher BMI than females.

Marital Status

Various researches were done and found Married people to have a strong association with overweight among the health workers. Amougou *et al.*, 2019 and

Lim *et al.*, (2019) reported that married people were significantly associated with overweight. Likewise, Iwuala *et al.*, (2015) and Ondicho *et al.*, (2016) married staff were predictors for overweight. According Jeffery *et al.* (2002) found that married individuals were more likely to have a companion with whom to eat and may therefore eat more regularly, leading to weight gain. Additionally, Married men and women were found to be less conscious of their body weight as they were not actively seeking mates (Wilson, (2012). Mata *et al.* (2015) explains that before marriage women are likely to be sensitive to wards their body sizes in the intention to attract opposite sex. However, after marriage the incentive to maintain body image ceases. The married people being in a position of not searching for a new companion strongly predispose them to high BMI.

Furthermore, married people might experience low body activity that influence their increased body weight. Energy expenditure is an important influence upon high BMI, and daily activities and exercise would be expected to be lower among married people since parents have less time for exercise. According to Matazu *et al.*, (2019) found that majority of the married women had house maids to aid them in house activities that subjected them to reduced physical activities and lead to overweight. Therefore, less body activeness among the married ones might put them at risk of high BMI.

Income Status

The income status was revealed to be associated with overweight among the medical workers was associated with overweight in some previous studies. According to Iwuala *et al.*, (2015) found that health workers in Nigeria that earned below 200000 naira were associated with overweight. However, Amougou *et al.*, and Lim *et al.*,

(2019) at Yaoundé Hospital and, Malaysia respectively reported that low income among the health workers was not associated with overweight. Low-income might subject people to food insecurity that limit access a variety of food in a house hold and may eventually subject them to depend on majorly a particular cheap food that be might be of energy dense and in a combination with low body activity can lead to overweight and obesity. Smith *et al.*, (2016) identified that food insecurity was highly significant for overweight among the house holds that had food insecurity as a result of low income. Additionally, low income may be linked with skipped meals, snack consumptions and lack of money to join physical exercise support systems such as Jims, buying equipment for exercise, which are risk factors for overweight. On the other hand, low income may enforce people to do physical activities due to lack of personal transportations like cars, Motorcycle etc., this may make individuals do some walking, involve in household activities etc. that eventually balance the body energy. Therefore, income level might positively or negatively influence Individual's BMI.

House Hold Capacity

Some scholars identified that the number of family members influence a person's body weight. According to Lim *et al.*, (2019) and revealed that a house capacity of 5 and more people were predictors for overweight. Similarly, Taib (2019) the house hold number of 5 members and above was significantly associated with overweight among the health workers. The high number of households might affect the financial stand that call for extra finance to ensure that all family members have access to food at all times or else the family may end up depending on a particular food staff that may suffer from nutrient dense but caloric dense food, as such leading

to increased overweight. Therefore, a large family was an independent predictor for high BMI among the health workers in the previous studies.

Eating Habits

Certain studies have been done and found that eating habits were associated with overweight. Khan *et al.*, (2016) found that high-caloric diet intake increased the likelihood of overweight. Additionally, Alissa *et al.* and Duodu *et al.* (2015) found that the medical students who skipped breakfast and ate late in the night were associated with overweight. Similarly, the study done among the Nurses by Shiao *et al.*, (2019) at work station during their work shift, meals substitution with sugary drinks was associated with overweight. When the body consumes food that it cannot spend it results into energy imbalance. Similarly, skipping meals could subject one to overeat at their next meal, Chen *et al.*, (2019) reported that meals taken late in the night was linked with increased Cholesterol and triglyceride levels. Increased total and Low-density lipoprotein (LDL) cholesterol that was positively associated with nighttime energy and fat intake. Every 100-kcal additional EI at night was associated 1.08 mg/dL higher of LDL-cholesterol. Skipped meal lowers the blood sugar throughout the day and reduces exercise and physical activity. Therefore, at the next meal not only one is hungry, but also with low blood sugar levels making bad choices like eating at fast food restaurants or having large meals (Richard,2020).

Body Exercise

Previous researches identified that body exercise was linked with overweight. Khan *et al.*, (2016) and Maria *et al.* (2017) identified that low or lack of body physical activity was associated with overweight among the student health professionals. Similarly, Amougou *et al.* (2019); Kasu *et al.* (2015); and Ondicho *et al.* (2016)

identified that low or lack of body physical activity was associated with overweight and among the health care workers. Regular exercise program increases the metabolic rate that enables the body to burn more calories throughout the day and this could help to maintain a healthy body weight. Therefore, failure to carry out adequate physical exercise can easily lead to energy imbalance hence overweight.

Alcohol Consumption

Alcohol consumption was identified to be associated with overweight in relation to former studies. Monakali *et al.*, (2019) found that alcohol use was an independent predictor of overweight, among the Healthcare Professional Nurses in Eastern Cape, South Africa. Similarly, Nam *et al.* (2016) and Ondicho *et al.* (2017) reported that alcohol consumption was associated with overweight among healthcare workers in Kisumu East Sub County, Kenyan and Eastern Cape, South Africa. According to Alison Douglas, (2017), alcohol drinking is likely to influence the number of calories consumed. The alcohol drinks contain a certain number of calories and possibly people might less likely to practice dietary compensation to take account of liquid calories as it might similarly be to the non-alcohol beverages because people might find liquid calories less satisfying as they consume more quickly. Hence, most likely cause more calories consumption than the body can utilise leading to increased BMI.

Smoking

Smoking was identified to be linked with overweight in previous studies. Monakali *et al.*, (2019) found that smoking was significantly associated with overweight among the Healthcare Professional Nurses. Similarly, and Nam *et al.*, (2016) showed that smoking was an independent predictor for increased BMI among

the Health workers. While, Lim *et al.* (2019), reported that smoking was not significantly associated with overweight among the health workers of Malaysia but the scholar urged cautiousness interpretation of these findings. According to Bloom *et al.*, (2019) supports that smoking accelerates a reduction in BMI due to the fact that Tobacco contains nicotine responsible for overpowering one's appetite, leading to low intake of calories. The nicotine containing ingredient in cigarette affects individual's taste for food.

Knowledge

The formerly done researches identified association between knowledge and overweight. Florindo *et al.*, (2015), study done among community health workers to evaluate the association between knowledge, delivery of preventive counselling and personal behaviours among community health workers in Brazil. It was found that that 50% of them were overweight and majority of the health workers could involve in body exercise and provide counselling on physical exercise to population. However, they had little knowledge about the recommended or global strategy for physical activity promotion and healthy diet of the World Health Organization. Knowledge gap might affect behaviour change in relation to maintain a healthy body weight or failure such as food choices, preparation, frequency of food consumption, time for body exercise etc. People with low knowledge may make poor food choices like junk food consumption and fail to carry out body exercise. Low awareness could be a great deal in increasing the body weight.

Perception

The research found that there was a relationship between one's perception and overweight. Simfukwe *et al.*, (2017) showed that some African health workers who

believed that Skinny body was a sign of poverty and illness and having enough food should be eaten as much as possible because it is a sign of richness were associated with increased BMI. While Phetla *et al.* (2017) found that health workers in hospitals in Mpumalanga Province, South Africa who perceived themselves to be of normal weight were associated with overweight. An individual's opinion can put him /her at risk of increased body weight.

Occupational Factors

Duration in Service

The time taken in health service was found to be associated with overweight among the health workers. Samhat *et al.*, (2020) showed that health workers in Lebanon who had worked for the average of 9years were independently associated with overweight. Similarly, Firouzbakht *et al.* (2019) found that Work experience of 10 years and above was associated with overweight among female health care workers in the Caspian Journal of Internal Medicine in Iran. The time taken in service may predispose the health workers to a number of risk health lifestyle such as for overweight such as working in shifts of day and night, inadequate time for physical activities etc. These poor health life styles eventually impact on individual BMI. According to Saulle *et al.*, (2018) reported that health workers who worked night shifts for a long time were 1.21time more likely to have an increased BMI compared to day shift workers. Overweight was found to be associated with the period of time spent in service delivery among the medical workers.

Supervisory Work

Managerial positions were revealed to be interrelated with increased BMI among the health professionals in past studies. Nam *et al.*, (2016) found that

supervisory position was associated with overweight among the Healthcare Professional Nurses. The Managerial level among the health workers might be linked with reduced body activity but increased number of times in a sitting position that provides a situation of energy imbalance leading to increased BMI. Administrative work was revealed to be associated with overweight among the health professionals.

Work Shift

Brum *et al.* (2020) found that night shift workers presented 2.8 times higher odds of developing excess weight than the day shift among healthcare workers of a Brazilian University Hospital. Similarly, Almajwal *et al.* (2016) and Ondicho *et al.* (2017) found that night shift work was significantly related to overweight among healthcare workers. Whereas, Gomez *et al.*, (2016) found no statistically significant association between shift work and overweight among the employees of a health care setting in Medellin, Colombia. The night shift workers had less hours of sleep compared to people who worked in the daytime. Even though they slept more on their days off, did not regain the sleep deficit produced by the night working days. Night shift work might impact on the eating habits of the health workers such as skipping meals and replacing it with junk food. For example, 78.2% of the nurses that were in night shifts had uneven meals timing with an important reduction in the number of complete meals consumed during the day and an increase in the number of snacks consumed during night (Samhat *et al.*, 2020).

Summary of the Literature Gaps

The reviewed literature provided a sap short image of the health problem of overweight as well as its related factors among the health work force. However, they have some limitations as explained below:

All the reviewed literatures were found to have been done in various locations of which the intended study area was not inclusive. It would be better to carry out the same study among the health workers in Mulago National Referral Hospital to better understand the status of the problem in this particular Area. This is crucial to have a wider knowledge of the problem in order to facilitate the policy making decisions.

Additionally, some studies were carried out among a specific health care group of the nurses such as (Kyle *et al.*, Nam *et al.*, Lee *et al.*, 2016 and Lim *et al.*, 2019). While Duodu *et al.* (2015) studied among health workers. Studying a specific group may limit the general understanding of the problem across the health worker force. It would be better to study overweight among the health workers generally across the different carders to fully understand the problem and better come up with suitable interventions.

Therefore, the current study planned to investigate the risk factors for overweight among the health workers in Mulago National Referral Hospital Kampala Uganda, a location that had limited research. It included the different health care categories such as doctors, nurses, midwives' dentists, Medical officers etc. There were multiple factors for overweight among health workers ranging from individual and occupational. The prevalence and risks factors were assessed in varying countries. However, less was known in the area of study. Establishing the prevalence of overweight among health workers in Mulago National Referral Hospital was intended to direct interventions and for contribution to the available literature.

CHAPTER THREE

METHODOLOGY

Introduction

This chapter highlights the methodological features and procedure for conducting the study. These include the research design, location of the study, population of the study, Data source sampling techniques, data collection methods, Validity of the study tools, Ethical considerations, reliability of the study data processing and analysis. The operational structures are to be placed of high interest in this section.

Research Design

This research was an observational, cross-sectional study design. The investigator never provided any intervention but measured the outcome and the exposures in the study participants at the same time and studied their association (Acharya *et al.*, 2012). This study adopted quantitative research approached (Amin, 2005). This collected data from the participants in a numerical form by the use of closed ended questions with multichoice answers to investigate risk factors associated with overweight among the Health workers in Mulago National Referral Hospital. The association research design was employed to assess the risk factors related to the independent and the dependant variables among the health workers in Mulago National Referral Hospital, and the descriptive study described the situation in terms of frequencies and percentages. To answer the research objectives, the research employed an observational cross-sectional design.

Locale of the Study

The study was done in Mulago National Hospital situated at old Mulago Hill. Mulago hill is in north-central Kampala, the capital city of Uganda, Kawempe Division, one of the five administrative divisions of Kampala. It is approximately 4 kilometres (2.5 mi), by road, north of the city's central business district. The research was implemented in the 2 varying geographic places of Mulago National Referral Health facilities (Kawempe and Mulago hill).

The study area selection was based to the study done by Mutanda *et al.*, (2017) among the nurses in the Mulago National Hospital in Uganda. It assessed the prevalence and factors associated with musculoskeletal disorders and showed that 45.5% of the health workers had both musculoskeletal disorder and overweight. This study was a land mark to unfold an iceberg of overweight among a proportion of health workers. Hence, the study area was selected to assess the prevalence and risk factors for overweight among the health worker force. Therefore, the research done among the medical staff in the Mulago National Hospital in Uganda by Mutanda *et al.*, (2017), provides the basis for the current study.

Population and Target Population of the Study

The study population consisted of health workers in Mulago National Referral Hospital in Kampala, Uganda and included the Doctors, Nurses, and Midwives, dentists, Laboratory technologists and Pharmacists. The previous study done by Mutunda (2017), concentrated on nurses only yet health workforce involves various carders that should equally be at the frontline in the prevention of communicable diseases as well as the lifestyle diseases related to overweight like hypertension,

diabetes and among others. They go through training and get knowledge and skills to enable them carry health promotion among the community they serve as well as their personal lives. The research population comprised of medical personnel of 18 years and above in National Referral Hospital, Mulago, and Kampala, Uganda.

Sample Size

The Simplified formula for proportions was used to calculate the sample size (Yaman, 1967).

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N * (e)^2}$$

N-the population size, n=sample size, e-acceptable error and this was assumed at 95% confidence level = 0.05. The population of the Medical professional workers in Mulago National Hospital in 2014/15 was 1820, according to the parliament report during the oversight to Public health facilities in Kampala and eastern Uganda. $n = N / [1 + N (e)^2] = 1820 / [1 + 1820 (0.05)^2] = 328$. The required calculated sample size was 328 health workers and was suitably a representative size for inferences.

Sampling Procedure

Sampling is a process of selecting the study participants from a population. Stratified sample random sampling technique was, being employed in this study. The sampling frame in this study included all the health workers in Mulago National Referral Hospital. The health workers were stratified according to their different professional cadres. The total number for each stratum was ascertained using the human resource record, and then the proportionate sample size was calculated with the formula; (sample size/population size) x stratum size. The respective sample from each stratum was selected by simple random technique where by numbers were assigned which were written on papers put in a basket, shaken well and picked one by one until the sample per stratum was reached. Stratified simple random technique

was employed in this study as it provides a high dimensional data (Huang et al, 2013).

Table 1: Stratification of the Population

Categories	Staff #	Calculation Sample size/population size) ×stratum	Required number of participants
Doctors	128	$328/1820 \times 128$	23
Nurses	901	$328/1820 \times 901$	162
Midwives	516	$328/1220 \times 516$	93
Lab Technicians	137	$328/1820 \times 137$	25
Dentists	96	$328/1820 \times 96$	17
Pharmacist	42	$328/1820 \times 128$	8
TOTAL	N=1820		n=328

Data Collection Methods and Instruments

The study collected primary data from eligible participants by both structured questionnaire and Anthropometric instruments. The questionnaire included closed ended questions with multiple choice answers from which the respondents selected that was self-administered. The questionnaire was written in the suitable language of the respondents (English). While the anthropometric measures for weight and height were done by a mobile weighing machine and height measure. The respondents' weight was measured in kilograms and height in feet, the participants took off their shoes and any other loads like hand bags, phones, books etc. before standing on the weighing machine to enable a proper approximate measure and height was also taken while each participant was in a standing position without shoes. Thereafter, the measurements were recorded and entered into CDC computerized BMI calculator that provided the BMI in kilogram/m².

The data collection was done by the help of the research assistants. The researcher identified 2 research assistants who had a medical background and research experience to help with the data collection exercise. They were trained about the protocol, data collection tools and ethical issues prior to study implementation. The training was done in a day, with some breaks between sessions. Therefore, data collectors were well conversant with the research procedures prior the study activity implementation.

Validity and Reliability

Prior to data collection, the validity and reliability of the questionnaire were ascertained. The validity of the questionnaire confirmed when the supervisors' checked the relevance of each question in providing answers to the study objectives, and appropriate modifications were made. Then, a content validity index C.V.I was computed using the formula:

$$\text{C.V.I} = \frac{\text{Number of relevant items in the instrument}}{\text{Total number of items in the questionnaire}} = 34/36$$

Total number of items in the questionnaire

The instrument was considered valid because the CVI was 0.94, that was greater than 0.6 as recommended by (Amin, 2005).

The reliability of the questionnaire was ensured after a pilot study that was done on 20 respondents in one of the health facilities which was not part the study sites and the respondents in the pretest of the questionnaire were not part of the real data collection. This aimed at obtaining responses that was like those expected from the participants in the final study. Not many health workers (20) were identified and each was asked to respond based on the content of the questionnaire. While completing the questionnaire, each was asked to think out loud and share what came to their mind on each question. They were asked whether they understood the

questions and which questions attracted a sense of discomfort and what options they could provide. Thereafter, changes in the question phrasing and structuring were made.

Data Collection Procedure

The investigator ensured all the required regulatory requirements prior data collection. She got a letter from the Dean of school of Graduate Studies (Bugema University) that followed IRB approval letter. This was presented to the administrator of Mulago National Referral Hospital who granted permission for the investigator to access the research sites of Kawempe and Mulago Hill health facilities. Unless the investigator got approvals from the IRB of Mulago and permission from Mulago Hospital Administration the study implementation would not have been possible.

The investigator of this study followed all required integrity throughout the research process. The researcher ensured voluntary participation and confidentiality of the participants, followed all the ethical guidelines that included getting informed consent from the respondents before any study procedure, ensured that respondents were aware of their voluntary participation and could withdraw from participation at any time if they decided. Moreover, anonymous questionnaire forms were used during the data collection and their custody was safeguarded. The researcher maintained ethical considerations prior and after data collection.

The research assistants were responsible for quality data collection. They identified eligible participants and provided them with questionnaires that were self-administered. They measured height and weight for every respondent, and reviewed the collected data for completeness while in the field. Then they took the completed questionnaires to the investigator who also performed a second review on

the completed questionnaires. Hence, valued data was prioritized in this study by both the research assistants and investigator.

The study was carried out during the COVID 19 pandemic that required the investigator to consider prevention measures during the data collection. The investigator used social distancing, facial mask and hand sanitizing while interacting with the research assistants and research regulatory bodies. Similarly, both the research assistants and study participants ensured social distancing, hand sanitizing and facial masks as COVID 19 preventive precautions. Therefore, the current guidelines for COVID 19 prevention were observed during the study implementations.

Data Analysis

STATA Microsoft ware was used in the analysis of descriptive and inferential statistic. Data was cleaned and entered into Epidata info then exported to STATA Microsoft ware. The frequencies as well as frequency tables were generated specifically for objectives 1 and 2; objective 3 was examined by use of bivariate and multivariate logistic regression tests. Chi-square test was used to analyse bivariate data to identify association between the independent and dependant variables. At bivariate analysis level, factors with a P-value of <0.05 were considered statistically significant and therefore associated with the dependant variable. Thereafter, factors that were associated with the dependant variable were subjected to multivariate logistic regression analysis with adjusted Odds. All variables with P-values less than 5% were considered significantly associated with the dependant variable. The computer processed P- value was found less than the level of significance set at 0.05, the null hypothesis was rejected. The quantitative statistics of this study was technologically concluded with STATA software.

CHAPTER FOUR

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This study presents the findings of the investigation of the risk factors and prevalence of Overweight among the Health workers of Mulago National Referral Hospital Kampala, Uganda. The specific objectives were to; describe the individual and occupation characteristics of the health workers of Mulago National Referral Hospital Kampala Uganda, determine the prevalence of overweight among the health workers of Mulago National Hospital, Kampala, Uganda and assess an association between individual and occupational factors with overweight among the health workers of Mulago National Referral Hospital, Kampala, Uganda. The sample size was 328 health workers with a response rate of 93% (306) and non-response rate of 7% (24). Therefore, the researcher managed to analyzed data for only 306 health workers. The findings of the study were presented and discussed in line with the study objectives.

Individual and Occupational Characteristics

The objective 1 was to describe the individual and occupational characteristics of the health workers in Mulago National Referral Hospital. The frequencies and percentages were used to determine the most frequently occurring responses and the least frequencies responses. The tables 2 and 3 below showed in detail the Items considered for analyzing the individual and occupational characteristics.

Table 2: Individual Characteristics

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Age 38.7±9(Mean±SD)	<30years	51	16.7
	30-39years	107	35.0
	40-49years	104	34.0
	>49years	44	14.4
Marital Status	Married	217	70.9
	Single	89	29.1
Gender	Female	227	74.2
	Male	79	25.8
Income status	100,00-300,000/=	11	3.6
	400,000-600,000/=	15	4.9
	700,000-900,000/=	88	28.8
	≥1,000,000/=	192	62.8
Household capacity	<5people	176	57.5
	≥5 people	130	42.5
Eating habits	Poor	233	76.1
	Good	73	23.9
Physical activity	Inactive	119	38.9
	Active	187	61.1
Alcohol consumption	Yes	34	11.1
	No	272	88.9
Smoking	Yes	22	7.2
	No	284	92.8
Nutritional knowledge	Low		69.9
	High	56	18.3
Perception	Wrong perception	214	69.9
	Correct perception	92	30.1

Age

Regarding the Age of the Health workers, Table 2 above showed that the mean age was 38.7±9.0 years. The majority of the respondents were within age bracket of 30-49years (35%) and 40-49years (34%). The majority of the study participants were females (74.2%). Large proportions (70.9%) were married, 62.8% had their monthly earning ≥1.000.000/= Ugandan shillings. 57.5% had a house hold capacity of ≤5people and 42.5% had ≥5people. The majority had a poor eating habit with 76.1%, 61.1% involved in physical activities while 38.9% had physical inactiveness. The respondents were found with smoking and alcohol consumption to a smaller extent (7.2% and 11.1% respectively). The majority of the respondents (81.7%) had no

Nutritional knowledge. 66.9% had wrong perception about overweight and 30.1% had correct perception.

Table 3: Occupational Characteristics

Variables	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Duration in service	<1year	5	1.6
	1-5years	68	22.2
	6-10 years	99	32.3
	≥10years	134	43.8
Work schedule	Night	118	38.6
	Day	188	43.8
supervisory Work	Yes	78	25.49
	No	228	74.51

Regarding the occupational characteristics, Table 3 showed that most of the respondents had worked between 6-10years (32.4%) and ≥10years were (43.8%). The majority of the respondents 61.4% worked day schedule while 38.4% were for night duties, 25.9% were found in supervisory work while 74.51% were not supervisors.

Objective 2 was to determine the prevalence of overweight among the Health workers in Mulago National Referral Hospital, Kampala Uganda. The frequencies and percentages were used to determine the most frequently occurring responses and the least frequent responses. The table 4 below showed the details of items considered for analyzing the prevalence of Overweight among the Health workers in Mulago National Referral Hospital.

Table 4: Prevalence of Overweight among the Health workers in Mulago National referral hospital

Variable	Categories	Frequency	Percentage
Adjusted BMI	Over-weight	Yes	222 72.5%
		No	84 27.5%

The prevalence of overweight among the Health workers of Mulago National Referral Hospital was 72.5%. This was higher than the prevalence of 44.7% identified among the health workers in Tertiary health facility, Lagos (Lwuala *et al.*, 2015). However, it was slightly higher than the prevalence of 58.8% and 68.9% found among the health care workers in Kenya, Kisumu East subcounty and Scotland respectively (Ondicho *et al.*,2016; Kyle *et al.*,2017).

Association between the Individual Factors and Overweight among the Health Workers in Mulago National Referral Hospital

Objective 3 of the Study was to establish whether individual and occupational factors were associated with overweight among the Health workers in Mulago National Referral Hospital. The table 5 below showed the details of items considered for analyzing the associated factors using the chi square statistical test at 95% confident interval.

Individual Factors

Age

The findings in table 5 indicated that age was associated with overweight ($\chi^2=9.871$, $p=0.02$). This was found to be in line with the previous studies done by (Lim *et al.*, 2019; Ondiocho *et al.*, 2016; Lwula *et al.*, 2015) that found that ones' age was associated with overweight.

Marital Status

The finding in the table 4 indicated no association between one's marital status and overweight ($\chi^2=1.013$, $p=0.314$). This result was found to be contrary to the previous studies that found that married people had a strong association with overweight (Lwuala *et al.*,2015; Amougou *et al.*, and Limet *et al.*,2019).

Table 5: The Association between Individual and Occupational Factors

Variables	Categories	Overweight		Chi-square	d f	P-value
		No	Yes			
Age 38.7±9.0(Mean±SD)	<30years	22(43.1)	29(56.9)	9.871	3	00.2***
	30-39years	30(28.0)	77(72.0)			
	40-49years	25(24.0)	79(76.0)			
	>49years	7(15.9)	37(84.1)			
Marital status	Married	56(25.8)	161(74.2)	1.013	1	0.000
	Single	28(31.5)	61(68.5)			
Gender	Female	57(25.1)	170(74.9)	2.419	1	0.120
	Male	27(34.2)	52(65.8)			
Income status	100,000-300,000	2(18.2)	9(81.8)	0.524	3	0.914
	400,000-600,000	4(26.7)	11(73.3)			
	700,000-900,000/=	24(27.3)	64(72.7)			
	≥1,000,000/=	54(28.1)	138(71.9)			
Household capacity	<5people	54(30.7)	122(69.3)	2.171	1	0.141
	5&more people	30(23.1)	100(76.9)			
Eating habits	Poor	68(29.2)	165(70.8)	1.474	1	0.225
	Good	16(21.9)	57(78.1)			
Physical activity	Inactive	43(36.1)	76(63.9)	7.373	1	0.007***
	Active	41(21.9)	146(78.1)			
Alcohol consumption	Yes	11(32.4)	23(67.7)	0.462	1	0.497
	No	73(26.8)	199(73.2)			
Smoking	Yes	11(50.0)	11(50.0)	4.31	1	0.038***
	No	70(28.0)	180(72.0)			
Nutrition knowledgeability	Yes	14(25.0)	42(75.0)	0.207	1	0.649
	No	70(28.0)	180(72.0)			
Perception	Wrong perception	52(243)	162(75.7)	3.551	1	0.06*
	Correct perception	32(34.8)	60(65.2)			

Statistical significance level=0.05

Gender

The finding in table 4 indicated that there was no association between one's gender and overweight ($\chi^2=2.419$, $p=0.120$). This was found contrary to some of the previous studies that found male gender to be significantly associated with overweight (Khan *et al.*, 2016; Maria *et al.*, 2017). However, in other studies gender was analysed at descriptive analysis and found that being female was more prevalent with overweight compared to males such as (Lim *et al.*, 2019; Ondicho *et al.*, 2016; Lwuala *et al.*, 2015).

Income Status

The findings in the table 4 indicated that there was no association between one's income status and overweight ($\chi^2=0.524$, $p=0.914$). This was found not in

agreement with the results from the previous study done among the medical workers that found an association between the people who earned 200000 naira (1928000/= Ugandan shillings) were associated with overweight (Iwuala *et al.*, 2015).

Household capacity

The findings in the table 4 indicated that there was no association between the house hold capacity and overweight ($\chi^2 = 2.171$, $p=0.141$). This result was found contrary to the results found in the previous study that found that house hold capacity ≥ 5 people was significantly associated with overweight (Lim *et al.*, and Taib, 2019).

Eating Habits

The findings in table 4 indicated that there was no association between the eating habits and overweight ($\chi^2 = 1.474$, $p=0.225$). This result differed from that found in the previous studies (Alissa *et al.*, and Duodu *et al.*, 2015) which found that poor eating habits such as skipping meals was associated with overweight among the health workers while meal substitution was an independent predictor for overweight (Shiao *et al.*, 2019).

Physical Activity

The finding in table 5, indicated that there was an association between physical inactiveness and overweight ($\chi^2 = 7.373$, $P=0.007$). This result agrees with the results from the previous studies which reported that people who never carried out physical exercises were associated with overweight (Khan *et al.*, 2016 and Maria *et al.*, 2017). However, findings in table 7, at multivariant logistic regression analysis indicated that people who physically inactive were significantly associated with overweight with AOR=1.923, 95% CL; [1.127-3.279], $P=0.016$. This implied that the respondents who carried out physical activities were 1.92times more likely to be overweight than those who never carried out physical exercises. This might have been

due to the fact that the respondents started to carry out physical activities after having gained weight in response to reduce weight.

Alcohol Consumption

The findings in table 5 indicated that there was no association between alcohol consumption and overweight ($\chi^2 = 0.462$, $P=0.497$). This result was found contrary to the findings from the previous studies that found alcohol consumption to be associated with overweight among the health workers (Nam *et al.*, 2016 and Ondicho *et al.* 2017). While Monakali *et al.*, (2019), reported that alcohol consumption was an independent predictor for overweight among the health workers in Eastern Cape, South Africa.

Smoking

The findings in table 5 indicated that there was an association between smoking and overweight ($\chi^2 = 4.31$, $P=0.038$). Similarly, Monakali *et al.*, (2019) and Nam *et al.*, (2016) reported association between smoking and overweight among the health workers. This could be that people who smoke might not take precautionary measures to maintain a normal weight such as lack of body exercise, poor eating habits etc.

However, in the findings from table 7 at multivariate regression analysis smoking was not significantly associated with overweight. Likewise, Lim *et al.*, (2019) found no significant association between smoking and overweight among the health workers in Malaysia. Bloom *et al.*, (2019) support that Tobacco contains nicotine, a substance that affects one's taste for food. Additionally, people who smoked might have observed other health life styles such good eating habits and carrying out physical exercise.

Nutritional Knowledge

The findings in table 5 indicated that there was no association between nutritional knowledge and overweight ($\chi^2 = 0.207$, $P = 0.649$). However, Florindo *et al.*, (2015), at descriptive analysis found that 50% of the health workers who had overweight majority of them had no knowledge about the recommended physical exercise and health diet.

Perception

The finding in table 5 indicated that there was no association between the one's perception and overweight ($\chi^2 = 3.551$, $P = 0.06$). However, results in table 7 indicated that perception (wrong perception) was significantly associated with overweight with AOR=0.533, 95%, CI; [0.304-0.934], $P = 0.028$. This implied that those who articulated overweight with value such as respect, wealth and good diet were 53% more likely to be overweight. Similarly, Simfukwe *et al.*, and Phetla *et al.*, (2017) reported that health workers who had overweight perceived that skinny body was a sign of poverty and believed themselves to be of normal weight.

Occupational Factors

The Association between Occupational Factors and Overweight, among the Health Workers in Mulago National Referral Hospital.

Table 6 below showed the details about the occupational factors that were associated with overweight among the health workers in Mulago National Referral Hospital.

Table 6: The Association between Occupational Factors and Overweight

Variable	category	Overweight		Chi-square	df	p-value
		No	Yes			
Duration in service	<1year	2(40.0)	3(60.0)	3.675	3	0.299
	1-5years	23(33.8)	45(66.2)			
	6-10years	29(29.9)	70(70.7)			
	>10years	30(22.4)	104(77.6)			
Work schedule	Night	32(27.1)	86(72.9)	0.011	1	0.918
	Day	52(27.7)	136(72.3)			
supervisory work	Yes	15(19.2)	63(80.8)	3.552	1	0.059
	No	69(30.3)	159(69.7)			

Statistical significance level=0.05

Duration in Service

The finding in table 6 indicated that there was no significant association between the duration in service and overweight ($\chi^2=3.675$, $P=0.299$). However, there was relationship between duration in service and overweight. The more duration in service increased the risk of overweight. This result was found contrary to that of the previous studies of Samhat *et al.*, (2020) who found that the average duration time in service of 9years was independently associated with overweight among the health professionals in Lebanon while Firouzbakt *et al.*, (2019) reported that work experience of 10years and above was associated with overweight among the medical workers in Caspian Journal of Internal Medicine in Iran.

Work Shift

The finding in table 4 indicated that there was no association between the work schedule and overweight ($\chi^2=0.011$, $P=0.918$). Similarly, Gomez *et al.*, (2016), found no statistical significance between work shifts and overweight among health workers in Medellin, Colombia. However, Almajwal *et al.*, (2016) and Ondicho *et al.*, (2017) reported that night shift work was significantly associated with overweight among the health workers. Moreover, Brum *et al.*, (2020) reported that night shift

health workers had 2.8 times higher odds of developing excess weight than the Day shift workers.

Supervisory Work

The findings in table 4 indicated that individuals who held supervisory positions were associated with overweight ($\chi^2=3.552$, $P=0.059$). Likewise, Nam *et al.*, (2016), reported that health workers who held supervisory positions were associated with overweight. However, the findings in table 5 at multivariate analysis, indicated that supervisory position was not a predictor for overweight with AOR =0.732, 95%, CI; [0.367-1.457], $P=0.374$. This could be due to the fact that people in supervisory position are likely to have less time to involve in active work but more in computer and also supervisory work might predispose them to lack of time to have proper eating lifestyle. For example, may tend to skip meals and consume repacked foods that are high in caloric dense food other than nutrient dense.

The Multivariate Analysis to Determine the Significance in Association between the Independent and Dependent Variables

The objective 3 of the study was to establish an association between the individual and occupational factors with overweight among the health workers in Mulago National Referral Hospital. To determine the significant association, all the variables in table 5 and 6 that showed an association at bivariate analysis were subjected to multivariate logistic regression analysis and adjusted odds ratio (AOR) at 95% confident interval and results are indicated in table 7 below.

Table 7: Individual and Occupational Factors Significantly Associated With Overweight

Predictors of overweight	Overweight		COR (CI95%)	AOR (CI95%)	P-Value
	No	Yes			
Age					
<30years	Reference		1	1	
30-39years	30(28.0)	77(72.0)	2.234[1.233-4.567]	2.110[1.025-4.346]	0.043
40-49years	25(24.0)	79(76.0)	2.225[1.564-4.989]	2.324[1.107-4.876]	0.026
>49years	7(15.9)	37(84.1)	4.001[1.578-13.671]	3.094[1.355-11.249]	0.012
Physical Activity					
Active	Reference		1	1	
Inactive	43(36.1)	76(63.9)	0.691(0.112-0.991)	0.520[0.305-0.887]	0.016
Smoking					
No	Reference		1	1	
Yes	11(50.0)	11(50.0)	0.433[0.032-1.242]	0.396[0.136-1.152]	0.089
Perception					
Correct perception	Reference		1	1	
Wrong perception	52(243)	162(75.7)	1.541[1.002-3.561]	1.878[1.071-3.293]	0.028
Supervisory Work					
No	Reference		1	1	
Yes	69(30.3)	159(69.7)	0.657[0.458-1.899]	0.732[0.367-1.457]	0.374

Statistical significance level=0.05

Age

The findings in table 7 indicated that age above 30years was significantly associated with overweight. The age bracket of 30-39 years was found with AOR=2.110, 95%, CI; [1.025-4.346], P=0.043, 40-49years was found with AOR=2.324, 95%, CI; [1.107-4.876], P=0.026 and >49 years was found with AOR=3.094, 95%, CI; [1.355-11.249], P=0.012. This implied that the age bracket of 30-39 and 40-49 years were twice more likely to be overweight while those who were above 49years were three times more likely to be overweight. However, the findings in the current study slightly differed from the previous studies that found that age above 40 years was significantly associated with overweight among the health workers (Lim *et al.*, 2019; Ondiocho *et al.*, 2016; Lwula *et al.*, 2015). Therefore, as people advance in age the risk of overweight increases and interventions to target health workers before advanced age can help to reduce overweight.

Physical Exercise

The results in table 7, indicated that body inactiveness was significantly associated with overweight with AOR=1.923, 95% CL; [1.127-3.279], P=0.016. The respondents who never exercised their bodies were 1.92 times more likely to be overweight compared to those who exercised. These findings were in line with that reported in previous studies that found that low or lack of physical activities among the health workers was a predictor for overweight (Amougou *et al.*2019; Ondiocho *et al* 2016 and Kasu *et al.*,2015). This implies that targeting interventions that enable the health workers to carry out physical exercises as recommended by MOH can help to reduce overweight.

Smoking

The finding in table 7 above, indicated that smoking was not significantly associated with overweight with AOR=0.396, 95%, CI [0.136-1.152], P=0.089. Similarly, Lim *et al.*, (2019) found no significant association between smoking and overweight among the health workers in Malaysia. However, some studies reported that smoking was a predictor for overweight among the Health workers (Monakali *et al.*, 2019 and Nam *et al.*, 2016). Therefore, smoking may reduce an individual's BMI due to the nicotine content that tends to reduce appetite leading to decreased caloric intake as it was supported by (Bloom *et al.*, 2019).

Perception

The results in table 7 indicated that wrong perception was significantly associated with overweight with AOR=0.533, 95%, CI; [0.304-0.934], P=0.028. However, the finding in table 5 indicated that there was no association between the one's perception and overweight ($\chi^2 =3.551$, P=0.06). This implied that those who articulated overweight with value such as respect, wealth and good diet were 53%

more likely to be overweight. This finding agreed with that in the previous study carried out in south Africa, which reported that health workers who perceived themselves to be of normal weight were significantly associated with overweight (Phetla *et al.*,2017). Therefore, interventions targeted to correct the wrong perception about overweight might contribute to reduction of overweight among the health workers.

Supervisory Work

The results in table 7 above showed no significant association between supervisory work and overweight with AOR=0.732, 95%, CI [0.367-1.457], P=0.374. However, the previous study reported a significant association between supervisory work and overweight among the health workers (Nam *et al.*, 2016).Therefore, being in a managerial position when considerations for health lifestyle are observed such as health eating, involving in physical activities etc may not affect one's BMI.

Hypothesis Testing

The hypothesis of the study stated that “there was no significant association between individual and occupational factors with overweight among the Health workers in Mulago National Referral Hospital but hypothesis test analysis from table 7 indicated that, factors with P value greater than 0.05 ($P>0.05$) such as smoking and supervisory position had no significant effect overweight. While factors such as Age, body inactiveness and perception were significantly associated with overweight among the health workers in Mulago National Referral Hospital with P value <0.05 and this supported the null hypothesis. The researcher accepts that, there was significant association between the risk factors for overweight among the health worker in Mulago National Referral Hospital as the multivariate logistic regression analysis indicated.

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This section of the study presents the summary of conclusion and recommendations of the study findings that were analyzed, presented and interpreted following the stated objectives and hypothesis on investigating the Risk factors and prevalence of overweight among the Health workers in Mulago National Referral Hospital, Kampala, Uganda.

Summary

Regarding the Individual and occupational characteristics, the mean age was 38.7 ± 9.0 years. The majority of the respondents were within age bracket of 30-49 years (35%) and 40-49 years (34%). The majority of the study participants were females (74.2%). The large proportions (70.9%) were married, 62.8% had their monthly earning $\geq 1,000,000$ Ugandan shillings. 57.5% had a house hold capacity of ≤ 5 people and 42.5% had ≥ 5 people. The majority had a poor eating habit with 76.1%, 61.1% were physically active and 38.9% were physically inactive. The respondents were found with smoking and alcohol consumption habits to a smaller extent (7.2% and 11.1% respectively). The majority of the respondents (81.7%) were not knowledgeable about overweight and the current recommended physical activity strategy. 66.9% had wrong perception about overweight and 30.1% had correct perception. While the occupational characteristics, most of the respondents had worked between 6-10 years (32.4%) and ≥ 10 years were (43.8%). It was found that more than half of the respondents (61.4%) worked day schedule and 38.4% were for night duties. The 25.9% of the respondents were found in supervisory work while 74.51% were not supervisors.

Regarding the prevalence of overweight, the health workers in Mulago National Referral Hospital were with 72.5%. The association of individual and occupational factors with overweight, findings showed that age ≥ 30 years was a significant factor for overweight. 30-39 years was found at AOR=2.110, 95%, CI:[1.025-4.346], P=0.043, 40-49 year was found with AOR=2.324, 95% CI:[1.107-4.876], P=0.026 and >49 years was found with AOR=3.094, 95% CI; [1.355-11.249], P=0.012; people who were not physically active were significantly associated with overweight with AOR=1.923, 95%, CI:[1.127-3.279], P=0.016 and those with wrong perception were significantly associated with overweight with AOR=0.533, 95% CI:[0.304-0.934], P=0.028.

Conclusion

The key risk factors that influenced overweight among the health workers in Mulago National Referral Hospital Kampala, Uganda included; age of 30 years and above, poor perception regarding overweight and failure to carry out optimum physical exercise as recommended in the current guideline by MOH.

Recommendations

Ministry of Health: The available recommended physical activity strategy should be strengthened among the health workers e.g. by providing structures and time for carrying out body exercises at all health facilities.

Health Workers: The researcher suggests that the health workers should be provided with continuous sensitisation about the health-related issues regarding overweight and the importance of routine physical exercises prior age of 30 years.

Areas of Further Studies

Qualitative Studies should be done on challenges and perceptions of health workers towards overweight.

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Daerah Melaka Tengah Department of Community Health, *Faculty of Medicine Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia*, Jalan Yaacob Latiff, Bandar Tun Razak, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia. 2. Pejabat Kesihatan Daerah Melaka Tengah, Jalan Bukit Baru, Melaka, Malaysia.

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APPENDICES

Appendix 1: Informed Consent Form

Title: RISK FACTORS AND PREVALENCE OF OVERWEIGHT AMONG HEALTH WORKERS IN MULAGO NATIONAL REFERRAL HOSPITAL KAMPALA, UGANDA.

Principal Investigator: BIRABWA JALIA, the researcher of this study is Postgraduate student of Bugema University in Public Health Nutrition finalist in the year 2020, contact; 0772673374, Email: jbirabwa12@gmail.com.

Purpose of the Study: Please read the following information carefully and ask the researcher if there is anything that is not clear or if you need more information. After you have heard the study explained and your questions answered and you have decided to participate, you will be asked to sign a consent form and you will be offered with a copy to keep.

It is important that you understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. The ultimate goal of this study is to investigate the risk factors associated with overweight and its prevalence among the health workers in Mulago National Referral Hospital. The purpose of this study is to investigate the risk factors and associated factors of overweight among the health workers in Mulago National Referral Hospital and its prevalence. The participant's weight, height and blood pressure will be taken by the research assistant and the self-administration questionnaire will be used to collect personal information.

Justification for the study population: Health workers should be at the frontline in the prevention of communicable diseases as well as the lifestyle diseases related to overweight like hypertension, diabetes and among others. They go through training and get knowledge and skills to equip them with health promotion among the community they serve as well as their personal lives.

Study procedure: This study is being conducted among the health workers in Mulago National Referral Hospital at the different locations of Kawempe, Kिररुदु and old Mulago. You have been sampled because you meet the study eligibility criteria for inclusion, and this consent form serves to provide you with all information pertaining

to the study. If you choose to participate you will be engaged in answering a self-administration questionnaire that will last about 30 minutes.

Risks: This research may cause negligible risks which will not be more than inconvenience in terms of time spent. No risk of harm or discomfort that will impact on the participant's life is fore seen.

Benefits: There will be no tangible benefits from the study. However, the findings will contribute to the available literature that may facilitate policy making for the good of the Health workers.

Compensation: There will be a reimbursement of five thousand Ugandan shillings (5000/=) for your time lost and inconveniences from the procedures.

Alternative to Participation: In case you are not interested in the study, you do not have to participate, no benefits will be lost. Your participation in this study will not affect your professional services that you provide in Mulago National Referral Hospital.

Summary of your Rights to Participate in This Study: Your participation is voluntary and you can withdraw consent at any time.

Confidentiality: Your responses to this survey will be anonymous. Every effort will be made by the researcher to preserve your confidentiality; Assigning code names/numbers for participants that will be used on all research notes and documents and any other identifying participant information will be in a locked file cabinet in the personal possession of the researcher. Participant data will be kept confidential except in cases where the researcher is legally obligated to report specific incidents.

Contact Information: If you have questions at any time about this study, or you experience adverse effects as the result of participating in this study, you may contact the researcher whose contact information is provided on the first page. If you have questions regarding your rights as a research participant, or if problems arise which you do not feel you can discuss with the Primary Investigator, please contact the chair of Institutional Review Board at Mulago, Dr. Nakwagala Frederick Nelson, **0772325869**

Consent: I have read and I understand the provided information and have had the opportunity to ask questions. I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time, without giving a reason and without cost.

I understand that I will be given a copy of this consent form and voluntarily agree to participate in this study.

Participant's signature _____ Date _____

Investigator: Name, Birabwa Jalia Signature _____ Date _____

Contact: 0772673374/070589409

Appendix 2: Questionnaire Form

My Name is Birabwa Jalia graduate student of Public Health Majoring in Nutrition of Bugema University; I'm carrying out a study on the RISK FACTORS AND PREVALENCE OF OVERWEIGHT AMONG HEALTH WORKERS IN MULAGO NATIONAL REFERRAL HOSPITAL KAMPALA, UGANDA. You have been selected to participate in this study by answering the preset questionnaire. Your participation is voluntary and you can withdraw your consent for participation anytime. The information got from you will be anonymous and will be treated confidential.

Health facility Proceeded by their codes (Tick) Kawempe [KP] <input type="checkbox"/> Mulago Hill [MG] <input type="checkbox"/>	Participant's Number (use Serio followed by facility code) Participant's Weight (kg) Height (cm)	DATE: <input type="checkbox"/>/...../..... Profession: Doctor <input type="checkbox"/> Midwife <input type="checkbox"/> Nurse <input type="checkbox"/> pharmacist <input type="checkbox"/> Dentist <input type="checkbox"/> Lab Tech <input type="checkbox"/>
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SECTION A: Social Demographical Factors

1. What is your age in years?.....
2. What is your marital status? 1 Married 2 Single
3. What is your gender? 1 Female 2 Male
3. What is your monthly earnings?
 1=100000-300000 2=400000-600000 3 =700000-900000 4≥1000000
4. How many numbers of people do you stay with and share the same meals, that include all the children adults and yourself
 < 5people = 1 ≥ 5people = 2

SECTIONB: Lifestyle factors

'Moderate-intensity activities' are activities that require moderate physical effort and cause small increases in breathing or heart rate like walking, digging etc.

8. Do you carry out any moderate physical activities?

1 Yes 2 No

9. How many days do you carry out moderate physical activities a week?

<3days=1 ≥3days =2

10. How long do you spend carrying out the moderate exercise on a particular day?

<30min=1 ≥30min=2

14. Do you currently drink alcohol?

1 Yes 2 No

16. Do you currently smoke tobacco or nicotine products? (**Tick**)

1 Yes 2 No

Eating Habits: 'Fast food' means any deep fried food such as chips, sour sages, fish, chicken, etc.

17. In the last one week did you consume fast food as your meal for breakfast or lunch or supper? 1 Yes 2 No

18. In the last one week have you ever skipped any of the meals like breakfast, lunch or supper? 1 Yes 2 No

19. If yes above, how many days did you skip the meal in the last one week?
.....days

20. In the last one week have you ever substituted or missed meals for a sweetened drink (e.g. soda, juice, tea etc.) or a snack (e.g. crisps, cake popcorn etc.)?

1 Yes 2 No

Knowledge :(Tick to what applies)

21. The BMI of an individual is got by:

- a) Weight in Kg and height in centimetres
- b) Dividing height in metres squared and weight in kg

22. The normal BMI should be between

- a) 18.5 -24.9
- b) 30 and above

23. BMI of 30 and above might lead to some of the non-communicable diseases like hypertension, Diabetes, cancers etc.

- a) Yes
- b) No

24. Currently increase in BMI has caused 'a **double burden**' of disease in Africa.

- a) Yes
- b) No

25. The High increase in BMI is both in developed and underdeveloped countries.

- a) Yes
- b) No

26. The recommended physical exercise for moderate should last for:

a) $\geq 30\text{min}$

b) $< 30\text{min}$

27. The recommended physical exercise should involve activities that cause an increase in breathing such as walking, digging etc.

a) Yes

b) No

28. The moderate physical exercise should be done on a weekly basis for at least;

a) 1day

b) 3days

c) 5days

29. Physical exercise carried out as recommended can reduce on the burden of non-communicable diseases.

a) Yes

b) No

30. The recommended Physical exercises are for all people at different age groups.

a) Yes

b) No

Perception: :(Tick to what applies)

31. People who are overweight are highly respected in the community

a) Yes

b) No

32. Overweight among people symbolises a good balanced diet

a) Yes

b) No

33. Overweight can also symbolise wealth and success. **(Tick)**

a) Yes

b) No

SECTION C: Occupational factors :(Tick to what applies)

34. How long have you worked in the health service delivery

$< 1\text{year}$

1-5years

6-10years

$> 10\text{years}$

35. What type of worker schedule do you always work?

1 Day duty

2 Evenings duty

3 nights duty

36. Do you hold a supervisory position at work?

1 Yes

2 No

You have come to the end of the survey, thanks you for the time.

Appendix 3: Data Collection Letter

BUGEMA UNIVERSITY

Main Campus
32km, Gayaza - Zirobwe Road
P.O. Box 6529
KAMPALA - UGANDA

Tel: 256-312-351400
Fax: 256-312-351460

Email: sgsbugema@gmail.com
Website: www.bugemauniv.ac.ug

Kampala Campus
2 miles Bombo Road
Between Total Petrol Station
& Makerere Yellow Primary Sch.
Muganzi-Awongerera Rd
P.O. Box 6529 KAMPALA - (U)

Tel: +256 312 266 629/30
+256 312 266 631

SCHOOL OF GRADUATE STUDIES

November 15, 2020

TO WHOM IT MAY CONCERN

RE: DATA COLLECTION

This is to certify that **BIRABWA JALIA**, Reg. No **18/MPH/BU/G/1002** is a student of Bugema University pursuing a Master's degree in **Public Health – Nutrition**.

The purpose of this letter is to request you permit her carry out data collection for her research entitled **"RISK FACTORS AND PREVALENCE ASSOCIATED WITH OVERWEIGHT AMONG THE HEALTH WORKERS IN MULAGO NATIONAL REFERRAL HOSPITAL KAMPALA, UGANDA"**.

The research will be based on utmost ethical considerations and the findings will be for academic purposes and of benefit to the Community.

Any assistance extended to her is highly appreciated.

Sincerely,

ROSETTE KABUYE, PhD.
DEAN, SCHOOL OF GRADUATE STUDIES

A CHARTERED SEVENTH-DAY ADVENTIST INSTITUTION

MISSION: "To offer an excellent and distinctive holistic Christian education designed to prepare our students through... for productive lives of useful service to God and to Society with uncompromising integrity, honesty and k..."

Appendix 4: IRB Letter

TELEPHONE: +256-41554008/1
FAX: +256-414-5325591
E-mail: admin@mulago.or.ug
Website: www.mulago.or.ug

MULAGO NATIONAL REFERRAL HOSPITAL
P. O. Box 7051
KAMPALA, UGANDA

IN ANY CORRESPONDENCE ON THIS
SUBJECT PLEASE QUOTE NO.....

10th November, 2020.

Ms. Jalia Birabwa
Principal Investigator
School of Graduate Studies
Bugema University.

Dear Birabwa,

Re: Approval of Protocol MHREC 1983: "Risk Factors and Prevalence of Overweight among Health Workers in Mulago National Referral Hospital Kampala Uganda".

The Mulago Hospital Research and Ethics Committee reviewed your proposal referenced above and granted approval of this study on 10th November, 2020. The conduct of this study will therefore run for a period of one (1) year from 10th November, 2020 to 9th November, 2021.

This approval covers the protocol and the accompanying documents listed below;

- Informed consent form
- Questionnaire

This approval is subjected to the following conditions:

1. That the study site may be monitored by the Mulago Hospital Research and Ethics Committee at any time.
2. That you will abide by the regulations governing research in the country as set by the Ugandan National Council for Science and Technology including abiding to all reporting requirements for serious adverse events, unanticipated events and protocol violations.
3. That no changes to the protocol and study documents will be implemented until they are reviewed and approved by the Mulago Hospital Research and Ethics Committee.
4. That you provide quarterly progressive reports and request for renewal of approval at least 60 days before expiry of the current approval.
5. That you provide an end of study report upon completion of the study including a summary of the results and any publications.
6. That you will include Mulago Hospital in your acknowledgements in all your publications.

I wish you the best in this Endeavour.

DR. NAKWAGALA FREDERICK NELSON
CHAIRMAN- MULAGO HOSPITAL RESEARCH & ETHICS COMMITTEE

Vision: "To be the leading centre of Health Care Services"